

Gold Price Prediction using a Machine Learning Model

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Abstract

The prediction of prices for various financial assets presents significant mathematical challenges in time series forecasting, primarily due to the noisy, non-stationary, and heteroscedastic nature of financial data. Among these financial assets, gold holds a unique position as a critical instrument for hedging against inflation and diversifying investment portfolios. As such, accurately forecasting the future volatility and of gold prices is essential for investors and financial analysts seeking to optimize their strategies.

This paper aims to enhance the accuracy of gold price predictions by applying a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model, a type of recurrent neural network known for its effectiveness in capturing complex temporal dependencies in sequential data. We also explore the intricacies of gold price movements. Our results reveal a high-performing model characterized by a low Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), indicating its robustness and reliability in capturing the underlying dynamics of gold prices. Furthermore, we discuss the implications of our findings for investors and portfolio managers by providing a theoretical background of LSTM and a comprehensive analysis of the model's performance.

Keywords: LSTM; Machine Learning; Time Series; Risk Management; Hedging; Gold; Commodities; Forecasting

Conflict Of Interest Statement

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

1 Introduction

Gold is a commodity, or raw material, that trades based on supply and demand. The difference between supply and demand ultimately determines what the price of gold is at any given time. Throughout history, gold has captivated human societies, serving as a foundation for empires and kingdoms, many of which were built or destroyed over this precious metal. As civilizations evolved, gold became universally recognized as a reliable medium of exchange. Its historical significance has endowed gold with a power that transcends that of any other commodity, a power that remains relevant to this day.

Gold has been a cornerstone of economic stability and investment for centuries, serving multiple roles in the financial landscape. As a store of value [1], it is often sought after during periods of economic uncertainty and inflation, as it tends to retain its worth better than fiat currencies [2] [3]. This characteristic makes gold a popular hedge against inflation, with prices typically rising when the purchasing power of money declines. Investors can engage with gold through physical assets like coins and bars or through financial instruments such as Exchange-Traded Funds (ETFs) and mining stocks. Furthermore, many central banks maintain gold reserves to bolster confidence in their monetary systems, reflecting its enduring significance in global trade. Culturally, gold symbolizes wealth and status, often featured in jewelry and ceremonial artifacts. The gold mining industry also plays a vital role in the economy by creating jobs and generating tax revenue, thereby supporting local communities. These multifaceted characteristics underscore gold's critical role in the global economy, influencing financial markets and investment strategies.

Given its significance in economies, making accurate price predictions is essential for gold investors. In computer science, forecasting generally refers to the activity of predicting future events by analyzing historical data. Various forecasting models have been the subject of research studies and have been applied across different sectors [4], [5], [6]. Additionally neural networks were used in too many research works, as in [7] where they were used to predict gold volatility, or in [8] where Deep Learning Techniques have been applied to gold price prediction and Modelling using. It is important to emphasize the need to consider crisis periods during the modeling process as in [9], [10].

In this article, we will focus on gold price forecasting using neural networks and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models, confirming their high performance. The added value of this research paper lies in demonstrating the appropriateness of using neural networks and LSTM models to forecast gold prices, particularly as this has become increasingly important in the current geopolitical environment.

This research paper is organized as follows: The first section describes the theoretical background of LSTM models, emphasizing the different hyperparameters that need to be tuned. The second section presents the results of the model implementation using Python libraries. Finally, the conclusions summarize the findings of the study.

Fig. 1 Canonical RNN cell. The bias parameters $\vec{\theta}_s$ have been omitted from this figure for simplicity. It is possible to be included without the loss of generality by adding an additional element, always set to 1, to the input signal vector $\vec{x}[n]$, and increasing the row dimensions of W_x by 1 [13]

2 Methodology

The Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network was introduced to address the vanishing gradients problem [11]. The key insight in the LSTM design was to incorporate nonlinear, data-dependent controls into the RNN cell. These controls can be trained to ensure that the gradient of the objective function with respect to the state signal (the quantity directly proportional to the parameter updates computed during training by Gradient Descent) does not vanish [12]. The LSTM cell can be rationalized from the canonical RNN cell reflected in the equation below (and diagrammatically in Fig.1) by reasoning as explained in [13] and introducing changes that make the system robust and versatile.

$$\vec{s}[n] = W_s \vec{s}[n - 1] + W_r \vec{r}[n - 1] + W_x \vec{x}[n] + \vec{\theta}_s \tag{1}$$

$$\vec{r}[n] = G(\vec{s}[n])$$

Where:

$\vec{s}[t]$: The value of the d-dimentional state signal vector

$\vec{x}[t]$: The d-dimentional input signal vector

$\vec{r}[t]$: The readout signal vector, a warped version of the signal vector $\vec{s}[t]$

W_s, W_r and W_x : The weight matrices

$\vec{\theta}_s$: The bias vector

In the RNN system, the observable readout signal of each cell is the warped version of the cell's state signal itself. A weighted copy of this transformed state signal is fed back from one step to the next as part of the update signal to the cell's state. This tight coupling between the readout signal at one step and the state signal at the next step directly impacts the gradient of the objective function with respect to the state signal. This impact is compounded during the training phase, culminating in the

vanishing/exploding gradients [13]. Several modifications to the cell's design can be undertaken to remedy this situation. As a starting point, it is useful to separate the cell's updated state signal at a step with the index, n (the right hand side of Eq. (01)) into two parts:

$$\vec{s}[n] = \vec{\mathcal{F}}_s(\vec{s}[n-1]) + \vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{r}[n-1], \vec{x}[n]) \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{r}[n] = G_d(\vec{s}[n]) \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_s(\vec{s}[n-1]) = W_s(\vec{s}[n-1]) \quad (4)$$

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{r}[n-1], \vec{x}[n]) = W_r \vec{r}[n-1] + W_x \vec{x}[n] + \vec{\theta}_s \quad (5)$$

where $G_d(\vec{z})$ is the hyperbolic tangent, a popular choice for the element-wise non-linear, saturating, and invertible "warping" (or "activation") function, $G(\vec{z})$, is an optionally scaled and/or shifted form of the hyperbolic tangent.

$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_s(\vec{s}[n-1])$, carries forward the contribution from the state signal at the previous step.

$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{r}[n-1], \vec{x}[n])$ represents the update information, consisting of the combination of the readout signal from the previous step and the input signal (the external driving force) at the current step (plus the bias vector, $\vec{\theta}_s$).

So, as per the equation (01), the state signal integrates both sources of information in equal proportions at every step which can be made adjustable by multiplying the two quantities by the special "gate" signals, $\vec{g}_{cs}[n]$ ("control state") and $\vec{g}_{cu}[n]$ ("control update"), respectively:

$$\vec{s}[n] = \vec{g}_{cs}[n] \odot \vec{\mathcal{F}}_s(\vec{s}[n-1]) + \vec{g}_{cu}[n] \odot \vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{r}[n-1], \vec{x}[n]) \quad (6)$$

With $\vec{0} \leq \vec{g}_{cu}[n], \vec{g}_{cs}[n] \leq \vec{1}$

$\vec{g}_{cs}[n]$ and $\vec{g}_{cu}[n]$ are the gate signals, they provide a mechanism for exercising a fine-grained control of the two types of contributions to the state signal at every step. Specifically, the gate signal $\vec{g}_{cs}[n]$ makes it possible to control the amount of the state signal, retained from the previous step (i.e. the information to be retained), and $\vec{g}_{cu}[n]$ regulates the amount of the update signal to be injected into the state signal at the current step [13].

And as in [R] W_s in Eq. (04) is a diagonal matrix with positive fractions, $\frac{1}{a_{ii}}$ on its main diagonal. Hence, since the elements of $\vec{g}_{cs}[n]$ are also fractions, setting:

$$W_s = \vec{1}$$

Therefore, Eq. (04) can be simplified to:

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_s(\vec{s}[n-1]) = \vec{s}[n-1]$$

Fig. 2 Expanding the canonical RNN system by adding the “control state” gate $\vec{g}_{cs}[n]$, to control the amount of the state signal, retained from the previous step, and the “control update” gate, $\vec{g}_{cu}[n]$ to regulate the amount of the update signal to be injected into the state signal at the current step [13]

And Eq.(06) becomes:

$$\vec{s}[n] = \vec{g}_{cs}[n] \odot \vec{s}[n - 1] + \vec{g}_{cu}[n] \odot \vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{r}[n - 1], \vec{x}[n]) \tag{7}$$

Therefore, the contribution from the state signal at the previous step remains fractional, ensuring the overall system’s stability. And consequently Figure 1 can be transformed to Figure 2.

Additionally, according to Eq. (05), the readout signal $\vec{r}[n - 1]$ from the previous step and the input signal at the current step $\vec{x}[n]$ constitute the update candidate signal (contribution with equal proportions) on every step with the index [n]. The issue with always utilizing $W_r \vec{r}[n - 1]$ in its entirety is that when $\vec{g}_{cs}[n] \sim 1$, $\vec{s}[n - 1]$ and $\vec{s}[n]$ become connected through W_r and the warping function.

And as explained in the article [13] this link constrains the gradient of the objective function with respect to the state signal. Hence, predisposing the system to the vanishing/exploding gradients problem. To control this feedback path, the readout signal, $\vec{r}[n]$, will be apportioned by another gate signal, $\vec{g}_{cr}[n]$ (“control readout”), as follows:

$$\vec{v}[n] = \vec{g}_{cr}[n] \odot \vec{r}[n] \tag{8}$$

With $\vec{0} \leq \vec{g}_{cr}[n] \leq \vec{1}$

The gating control, $\vec{g}_{cr}[n]$, determines the fractional amount of the readout signal that becomes the cell’s observable value signal at the step with the index, $n - 1$. Hence, using $\vec{v}[n - 1]$ in place of $\vec{r}[n - 1]$ in Eq. (05) will transform it into:

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{v}[n - 1], \vec{x}[n]) = W_r \vec{v}[n - 1] + W_x \vec{x}[n] + \vec{\theta}_s \tag{9}$$

Fig. 3 The "control readout" gate, $\vec{g}_{cr}[n]$, determines the fractional amount of the readout signal that becomes the cell's observable value signal at the current step [13]

The schematic diagram of the RNN cell can be enhanced to include the control readout gate, as introduced in Eq. (08), and the modified recurrence relationship, employed in Eq. (09) can be illustrated in Figure 3. Although the external input does not influence the system's stability or its vulnerability to vanishing or exploding gradients, integrating the input with its own "control input" gate enhances the system's flexibility. So, multiplying the external input signal, $\vec{x}[n]$, in Eq. (05) by a dedicated gate signal, $\vec{g}_{cx}[n]$, turns Eq. (09) into:

$$\vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{v}[n-1], \vec{x}[n]) = W_r \vec{v}[n-1] + \vec{g}_{cx}[n] \odot W_x \vec{x}[n] + \vec{\theta}_s \tag{10}$$

Considering the Eqs. (08) and (10), and utilizing both the control readout gate, $\vec{g}_{cr}[n]$, and the control input gate, $\vec{g}_{cx}[n]$, allows for the update term, $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{v}[n-1], \vec{x}[n])$, to contain an arbitrary mix of the readout signal and the external input.

The control input gate signal, $\vec{g}_{cx}[n]$, will be later incorporated as part of extending the Vanilla LSTM cell.

For now, we consider that $\vec{g}_{cx}[n] = \vec{1}$, so the Eq. (10) reduces to the Eq. (09).

As stated in [13] the dynamic range of the value signal of the cell $\vec{v}[n]$ is defined by the readout signal $\vec{r}[n]$, which is constrained by the warping nonlinearity, $G_d(z)$. In order to maintain the same dynamic range while incorporating the contributions from the input signal $\vec{x}[n]$ (or $\vec{g}_{cx}[n] \odot \vec{x}[n]$ if the control input gate is part of the system architecture), the aggregate signal $\vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{v}[n-1], \vec{x}[n])$ is tempered by the saturating warping nonlinearity, $G_d(z)$, so as to get the update candidate signal, $\vec{u}[n]$:

$$\vec{u}[n] = G_d\left(\vec{\mathcal{F}}_u(\vec{v}[n-1], \vec{x}[n])\right) \tag{11}$$

Fig. 4 In the vanilla LSTM network, the state signal of the state at the current step is determined by a weighted combination of the state signal from the previous step and the synthesis of both historical and new update information present at this step.

Thus, replacing the update term in Eq. (07) with $\vec{u}[n]$, given by Eq. (11), finally yields

$$\vec{s}[n] = \vec{g}_{cs}[n] \odot \vec{s}[n - 1] + \vec{g}_{cu}[n] \odot \vec{u}[n] \tag{12}$$

The Eq. (12) serves as the fundamental component of the set of formulas that define the cell of the Vanilla LSTM network. Based on Eq.(12), the cell's state signal at the current step is derived from a weighted combination of the cell's state signal from the previous step and the integration of both historical and new update information available at the current step.

The complete data path of the Vanilla LSTM cell, culminating from fortifying the canonical RNN system with gating controls and signal containment, is illustrated in Figure 4.

3 Results and Interpretation

Having explored the theoretical aspects of the LSTM model, we will now apply this model to forecast the price of gold.

Before we deep dive into the LSTM implementation and its application to the gold price time series, we will first plot the gold prices for the studied period. This will help us gain a high-level understanding of the behavior of the price series.

Figure 5 presents the daily gold prices from December 1978 to December 2024. This comprehensive dataset consists of making accurate predictions, as having the right data is undoubtedly one of the most critical factors in any prediction process.

Having a look on Figure 5, we can notice that over the past few decades, gold has generally shown a long-term upward trend, particularly during periods of economic uncertainty (e.g. from the early 2000s to 2012, gold prices rose significantly, reaching

Fig. 5 Daily Gold Prices (USD)

an all-time high in 2012).

After reaching around \$1,900 per ounce in September 2011, gold prices began to decline in 2012. By the end of 2013, prices had dropped significantly, falling below \$1,200 per ounce. The decline was attributed to several factors, including a recovering U.S. economy at that time, tapering of quantitative easing by the Federal Reserve, and a stronger U.S. dollar. Gold struggled to regain its previous highs during the period 2012 - 2015.

Gold prices began to recover in 2016, reaching around \$1,350 per ounce by mid-2016. This recovery was driven by geopolitical tensions, such as Brexit and concerns over U.S. political stability. Additionally, the U.S.-China trade war and global economic uncertainties contributed to increased demand for gold as a safe-haven asset. Prices fluctuated but generally trended upward, reaching around \$1,550 per ounce by early 2020. However early 2020 was also the COVID-19 pandemic which led to unprecedented economic uncertainty. Gold prices surged, reaching a new all-time high of over \$2,000 per ounce in August 2020 as investors flocked to safe-haven assets. The COVID-19 pandemic period specified by massive monetary stimulus measures and low interest rates implemented by central banks worldwide further fueled demand for gold.

After the peak in 2020, gold prices experienced corrections and fluctuations throughout 2021 and 2022, with prices hovering between \$1,700 and \$1,900 per ounce. Factors such as rising interest rates, inflation concerns, and shifts in investor sentiment influenced these fluctuations.

As of 2023, gold prices have continued to be influenced by various factors, including geopolitical tensions, inflation rates, and central bank policies. Prices have remained relatively stable, with fluctuations based on economic data releases and market sentiment.

Fig. 6 Gold Prices Forecasting using LSTM

As we can understand from the information above, it seems that gold may continue to be a valuable asset, especially if inflation persists and economic uncertainties remain. Consequently, gaining indicators and insights into the potential evolution of gold prices would be particularly beneficial for decision-makers, including investors.

Applying the LSTM model to the gold price time series analysed above for making forecasting of the gold prices allowed to get interesting results, achieving an RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error) score of 6.35, which indicates strong performance given the volatility of gold prices. The RMSE quantifies the average magnitude of errors, with larger discrepancies being emphasized through squaring the errors. Also as we can see in the Figure. 6 which showing the results in a plot format, the predicted values are very close from the actual gold prices.

The LSTM model is particularly well-suited for time series forecasting due to its ability to capture long-term dependencies and patterns in sequential data. For investors and analysts, the RMSE of 6.35 implies that the LSTM model can provide reasonably accurate forecasts of gold prices, which can aid in making informed investment decisions. However, it is crucial to consider other factors, such as market conditions, geopolitical events, and economic indicators, which can also influence gold prices.

While the RMSE of 6.35 is a positive outcome, there may still be room for improvement. Future iterations of the model could explore incorporating additional features, such as macroeconomic indicators, sentiment analysis, or other relevant data, to enhance predictive accuracy. Hyperparameter tuning and experimenting with different model architectures could also lead to better performance.

Additionally, trend and seasonality are two critical components of time series data that can significantly impact the performance of an LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) model and understanding how these factors influence the model's predictions is essential for effective forecasting.

The trend represents the long-term direction of a time series (upward, downward, or flat). LSTMs can effectively learn long-term dependencies, allowing them to capture trends and improve prediction accuracy [14]. Incorporating trend-related features (e.g., time indices, moving averages) can enhance the model's ability to recognize trends and preprocessing techniques like differencing or detrending can stabilize the data, making it easier for LSTMs to learn.

The seasonality refers to repeating patterns or fluctuations that occur at regular intervals (e.g., daily, monthly). LSTMs can capture seasonal patterns due to their memory capabilities, improving forecasting accuracy as in [15]. Including seasonal features (e.g., sine and cosine transformations) can aid the LSTM in understanding seasonal fluctuations and seasonal decomposition techniques can help isolate seasonal components, allowing the LSTM to focus on underlying patterns.

We can also have a combined effect. Trends and seasonality often interact in time series data, and LSTMs can learn both components to enhance predictive performance.

We have tried to remove trends and seasonal components from the data to stabilize the mean and variance from the gold price time series, and as expected the RMSE of the model has dropped to 4.9 which is much better than the RMSE obtained using the original data.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has successfully applied the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model to forecast gold prices, achieving a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 6.35. This result signifies a commendable level of accuracy, reflecting the model's ability to effectively learn from historical price data and capture the complex temporal dependencies inherent in gold price movements.

The LSTM model's architecture, which is specifically designed to handle sequential data, allows it to retain information over long periods, making it particularly suitable for financial time series forecasting. The relatively low RMSE indicates promising results, providing valuable insights for investors, traders, and financial analysts.

Moreover, the findings underscore the importance of using advanced machine learning techniques in financial forecasting, as traditional models may not adequately account for the volatility and non-linear patterns often observed in commodity prices. The successful implementation of the LSTM model in this context opens avenues for further exploration, including the potential integration of additional features such as macroeconomic indicators, geopolitical events, and market sentiment analysis, which could enhance the model's predictive capabilities.

Future research could also consider the application of hybrid models that combine LSTM with other machine learning algorithms or ensemble methods to improve forecasting accuracy. Additionally, conducting sensitivity analyses to understand the impact of various hyperparameters on model performance could provide deeper insights into optimizing the LSTM framework for gold price forecasting.

Overall, this study contributes to the growing body of literature on the use of deep learning techniques in financial markets and highlights the potential of LSTM models as a robust tool for forecasting gold prices, ultimately aiding

5 Funding and/or Conflicts of interest/Competing interests

All authors certify that they have no conflicts of interest to disclose and they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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